

TEACHING ENGLISH AS A SECOND OR FOREIGN LANGUAGE, MULTILINGUAL SETTING AND TEACHING TECHNIQUES

Juraeva Madinabonu Shermuhammad qizi

English Teacher of Tashkent State Transport University under academic lyceum

E-pochta: Djuraeva6660@gmail.com

ABSTARCT:

All living creatures have some means of conveying information to others of their own group, communication being ultimately essential for their survival. Some use vocal noises, others physical movement or facial expression. Many employ a variety of methods. Birds use predominantly vocal signals, but also show their intentions by body movements; animals use vocal noises as well as facial expressions like the baring of teeth; insects use body movements, the most famous of which are the various 'dances' of the bees.

Keywords: second language acquisition, general English skills, first language, foreign language, ELF, teaching and learning, multicultural, multiethnic, multilingual country, Language Center English classes, English courses, SEEU faculties, methodological strategies, different language, cultural and religious backgrounds, elementary and high school, "teacher-student" system.

INTRODUCTION:

The students enrolled at the SEEU ¹come from different ethnic backgrounds. The Language Center, which operates within this university, offers English courses to all students from all SEEU faculties, starting from general English skills up to academic and ESP. Having this mixture of teachers and students, the teaching and learning of English in this environment is rather challenging for both sides. The most challenging issue in teaching a foreign language (in our case English) is the concern of teachers on whether to use the learner's first language or not. This paper focuses on the question of whether there is a use of the L1 in ELF teaching at SEEU, Language Center English classes. If, yes, to what extent and in what occasion is it used? The paper examines and elaborates the methodological strategies that English teachers employ in order to accommodate and facilitate the needs of the students who have been raised and educated in a multilingual setting. The data collected for this paper were analyzed using quantitative and qualitative methods. In conclusion, the findings emerging from this

¹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/SeeU>

study suggest that balanced and careful use of L1 in the English classes seem not to affect the students' exposure to the target language.

Macedonia is very small but known as a multicultural, multiethnic, and multilingual country. While in elementary and high school, students are placed in the classes according to their nationality, at the university level they are mixed in one group. This diversity in the classes, especially when teaching a foreign language, sometimes brings many complications when it comes to using the L1. Poudel, P. P. (2010:121) defines multilingualism as “a condition in which more than two languages are used in the same setting for similar purposes”. The concern of teaching in such a diverse context comes from the fact that the teacher has to manage a class full of students from a different language, cultural and religious backgrounds. In such circumstances using students L1, might, in fact, waste the time designed for teaching and learning. Yet, another concern comes up if the teacher does not speak all the languages of the students in the classroom. On the other hand, if L1 is used, teachers must give equal opportunity to all students in order not to discriminate against any of them.

Being trained, teachers know that there are ways to demonstrate and explain vocabulary or any other linguistic problem by using synonyms, antonyms, gestures, or mime, and using these strategies may help teachers avoid the L1 use in the classes. Even though the Language Center policy is to only use English as a language of instruction, both teachers and students are tempted to use their L1 during the English classes. In this paper, I will discuss using the L1 in the English classes and its role in the process of acquiring the target language.

Literature review, Pros and cons of using the L1 in the English class, EFL¹ teachers, based on their experiences as learners of a foreign language; claim that the mother tongue has a beneficial role in second language acquisition and learning.

Using L1 has a great impact on the EFL learning process. Many scholars claim that learners acquire a second language by using the knowledge they already have of their native language. Implementing this strategy enables them to cope with communication difficulties and interactions. Studies have shown that learners rely on their background experiences and prior knowledge of their native language to acquire a second language. They use structures from their first language that are comparable to the second language transfer forms and meanings while attempting to read, speak or write the second language. Using L1 in EFL classes has been a very debatable question. This question has divided scholars into two groups.

¹ <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/efl>

On one hand, there are those who support the use of L1, such as Atkinson (1987), who strongly supports the theory that students' mother tongue shouldn't be completely ignored in the English classes since "the use of L1 can be very effective in terms of the amount of time spent explaining" (Atkinson, 1987:242). On the other hand, there are those who are against the use of L1, claiming that the overuse of L1 restricts the students' exposure to the target language. Among a number of teachers in second language acquisition, there seems to be an increasing conviction that the first language (L1) has a facilitating role in the second language acquisition (Schweer, 1999). Also, Ferrer, (2000) states that a good number of teachers guided from their experiences as learners of a second language claim that the mother tongue has an active and beneficial role in instructed second language acquisition learning. Stern (1992) suggests that L1 and L2 could not be considered apart as he argues that: "the L1-L2 connection is an indisputable fact of life, whether we like it or not the new knowledge is learned on the basis of the previously acquired language" (1992: 282).

In his research, he concludes that excluding the use of L1 will obstruct the comprehension of the target language effectively. The author continues explaining that if the learner lacks comprehension, one will not be able to achieve any success in learning the language; therefore, the author supports the use of L1 when it is considered necessary. Macaro (2005:532) points out that avoiding the L1 increases usage of input modification (e.g. repetition, speaking more slowly, substituting basic words for more complex ones, simplifying syntax, etc.) which is time-consuming as well as makes the teaching boring and less realistic. In line with these facts, Nunan and Lamb (1996) consider that L1 is inevitable during the learning process, particularly at low levels.

English Teaching Techniques, Since the builders of the Tower of Babel¹ spoke different languages, society began to need translators. Interpreters were appreciated everywhere. Until recently, foreign language was more of a hobby than a cruel reality. To know a foreign language meant to be an esthete, to belong to a certain circle, or (the most innocuous option) - to be known as an eccentric. But times are changing.

Any house, as you know, begins with an architectural plan. Now we are less and less frightened by a huge fortress called "Foreign Language", at the top of which a flag (most often British) flies proudly. And, in this case, knowledge of modern teaching methods will serve as this necessary plan. Recently, when the educational technology market is replete with proposals for a wide variety of methods of learning English, the question "What method do you use to teach?" becomes more and more relevant, which indicates an increase in the culture of consumption of intellectual products. A perplexed applicant, student, or businessman (however, also a student) increasingly

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tower_of_Babel

freezes in front of bookshelves with linguistic literature and media aids or pensively looks through a long list of advertisements. One of the selection criteria is the price, but the main one ... "English in two weeks", "Communicative methods of teaching English", "English with Englishmen in Moscow", "Effective express method", "English at the subconscious level", eventually. So much is new and unknown! And this gives rise to doubts about the results. Can you trust modern technology? Or give preference to well-established "brands" - such as "Bonk", "Eckersley" or "Headway", which are gradually moving into the category of methodological classics?

The fact remains that at the end of the XX century. In Russia there was a "revolution" in the methods of teaching English. Previously, all the priorities without a trace were given to grammar, almost mechanical mastery of vocabulary, reading and literary translation. These are the principles of the "old school", which (to give it its due) still bore fruit, but at what cost? Language acquisition was carried out through long routine work. The tasks were quite monotonous: reading the text, translating, memorizing new words, retelling, and exercises on the text. Sometimes, for the sake of the necessary change of activity, - an essay or dictation, plus phonetic drills as a rest. When priority was given to reading and working on "topics", only one function of the language was realized - the informative one. It is not surprising that only a few people knew the language well: only very purposeful and hardworking people could master it at a high level. But in terms of grammar proficiency, they could easily compete with Cambridge graduates! True, they received good compensation for their work: the profession of a teacher of a foreign language or a translator was considered very prestigious in our country.

Now, to achieve this still high social status, it also requires a lot of diligence, perseverance and daily work. But what is truly "revolutionary" is that language has become accessible to the majority in one form or another. And the offer is more and more consumer-oriented. Why, for example, would the secretary acquire knowingly unnecessary knowledge about the palatalization of consonants or the actual division of English sentences? A secretary-assistant or manager who has 8-hour, or, as it is now customary to say, "monopoly" office work, is focused on the development of very specific knowledge and skills, that is, on the consumption of a specific segment of the market for educational offers for learning English. ¹A well-known specialist in the field of linguistics and methods of teaching a foreign language S.G. Ter-Minasova rightly notes that recently, language learning has become more functional: "The unprecedented demand demanded an unprecedented supply."

¹ <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/overcoming-difficulties-in-teaching-english-as-a-second-language-to-adults-multilingual-settings-and-teaching-techniques>

Unexpectedly, foreign language teachers were in the center of public attention: legions of impatient specialists in various fields of science, culture, business, technology and all other areas of human activity demanded immediate teaching of foreign languages as a tool of production. They are not interested in either theory or history of the language - foreign languages, primarily English, they require exclusively functionally, for use in various spheres of society as a means of real communication with people from other countries". With the form of education, the situation has also become noticeably simpler: going to the office, one-on-one classes with a teacher, going home to a student, "weekend" groups, for busy and not so busy, for "pioneers" and retirees. The main question remains to be solved: what are the content of the course, its structure and teaching methods? Who is the author of the proposed material, where was this material developed and by whom was it tested?

Language teaching has acquired an applied character; while earlier it was comparatively abstract and theorized. Even Aristotle brought out the famous triad of teaching ethics, which correlates perfectly with modern requirements: logos - the quality of presentation, pathos - contact with the audience, ethos - attitude towards others. This rule is true for the speaker, and for the actor, and for the teacher of a foreign language, the role of which also assumes the first two hypostases. The functions of the teacher in the educational process have changed significantly. A teacher-mentor, a teacher-dictator, is not able to provide students with freedom of choice and provide the "freedom of learning" necessary in the comprehension of such a subtle matter as language. Therefore, such a negative pedagogical image is gradually becoming the property of history. He was replaced by an observer teacher, a mediator teacher, a "pacifier" teacher and a leader "Although the teacher's personality in this case fades into the background, its influence on the audience, which, in turn, becomes more intimate, does not diminish, but On the contrary, it is the teacher in most modern - Russian and foreign - courses who is the organizer of group interaction (a group of 10-15 people is currently considered an ideal team for learning a foreign language, since this is the number of people who can communicate with each other with maximum effect , interest and benefit).

Progress and fundamental changes in language learning methods are undoubtedly associated with innovations in the field of personality and group psychology. Now there are noticeable changes in the consciousness of people and the development of new thinking: the need for self-actualization and selfrealization, proclaimed by A. Maslow, appears. The psychological factor in the study of foreign languages is being promoted to a leading position. The authenticity of communication, balanced requirements, and claims, mutual benefit, respect for the freedom of other

people - this is a set of unwritten rules for building constructive relationships in the "teacherstudent" system.¹

The fifth, but by no means the least important element of this system is chosen. It comes from a student who can attend a course that best suits his needs. In the classroom, the student is no longer limited in the choice of speech means and his own speech behavior. The teacher is also not constrained in choosing: methods and techniques of teaching - from games and pieces of training to simultaneous translation; in the organization of classes; in the choice of textbooks and teaching aids - from a wide range of domestic publications to products from Oxford, Cambridge, London, New York, and Sydney. The teacher can now select, create, combine, modify.

Fundamental technique this is indeed the oldest and most traditional technique. This is exactly how the lyceum students taught Latin and Greek, while French was absorbed naturally, together with the strict suggestions of the governesses and communication with Maman and Papan. The classical method, like no other, fits the description of the "plan to capture the fortress": phonetics cipher, visual images of syntactic constructions, mandatory vocabulary ... The student clearly understands: to be known as Sir Calm, Monsieur Gallantry or Herr Sanity, he: a) is ready to spend 2-3 years; b) be patient (study starts from the beginning); c) I must remember how the subjects, the addition can be expressed in the native, "great and mighty", and what it is all about - syntax.

The fundamental methodology is seriously relied on in language universities. The translator is never sure of his knowledge of a foreign language, he perfectly understands the unpredictability of emerging speech situations. Studying according to the classical method, students not only operate with a wide variety of lexical layers but also learn to look at the world through the eyes of a "native speaker" - a native speaker.

Perhaps the most famous representative of the classical methodology of teaching a foreign language is N.A. Bonk. Her English textbooks, written jointly with other authors, have long become classics of the genre and have withstood the competition of recent years. The classical technique is otherwise called fundamental: no one promises that it will be easy, that you will not have to study at home and the teacher's experience will save you from mistakes in pronunciation and grammar. But the reward will be, developing the fortress metaphor, the state of a real local who knows how not to get lost in the labyrinth of the subjunctive mood or the past tense. And further. The fundamental methodology assumes that your favorite question is "why?" That you will not be content with explanations "it should be so", but are ready to plunge into an interesting, complex, and very logical world, whose name is the language system.

¹ https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---dcomm/---publ/documents/publication/wcms_833561.pdf

CONCLUSION:

The classic approach to learning a foreign language. In this regard, the classical approach to the study of a foreign language has also somewhat transformed, but the unshakable principles of the "classics" of Russian language methods have been preserved. Sometimes they are actively used in schools of other methodological directions. The classic course is aimed at students of different ages and most often involves learning the language "from scratch". The tasks of the teacher include traditional, but important aspects of the formulation of pronunciation, the formation of a grammatical base, the elimination of the psychological and language barriers that impede communication. "Classics" did not change the goals, but the methods, due to the new approach, are already different.

REFERENCES:

- 1) Aitchison, J. (1972) *General Linguistics*, English Universities Press.
- 2) Aitchison, J. (1978) *Linguistics*, Hodder & Stoughton, 2nd edn.
- 3) Alexander, L.G. (1971) *Guided Composition in English Teaching*, Longman.
- 4) Allen, J.P.B. and Corder, S.Pit (eds) (1974) *The Edinburgh Course in Applied Linguistics*, Vol. 3,
- 5) *Techniques in Applied Linguistics*, Oxford University Press.
- 6) Allen, J.P.B. and Corder, S.Pit (1977) *The Edinburgh Course in Applied Linguistics*, Vol. 4, *Testing and Experimental Methods*, Oxford University Press.
- 7) Anderson, W.L. and Stageberg, N.C. (1966) *Introductory Readings on Language*, New York: Holt, Rinehart & Winston.
- 8) Argyle, M. (1972) *The Psychology of Interpersonal Behaviour*, Penguin, 2nd edn.
- 9) Austin, J.L. (1962) *How to Do Things with Words*, Oxford University Press.
- 10) Bach, T. and Harris, F.L. (eds) (1968) *Universals in Linguistic Theory*, New York: Holt. Rinehart & Winston.
- 11) BBC/British Council (1976) *Teaching Observed*, 13 films with hand book.
- 12) Binham, P. (1968) *How To Say It*, Longman.
- 13) Bloomfield, L. (1935) *Language*, Allen & Unwin, revised British edn.
- 14) Bolinger, D. (ed.) (1972) *Intonation*, Harmondsworth: Penguin.
- 15) Bolinger, D. (1975) *Aspects of Language*, Harcourt Brace Jovanovich 2nd edn.
- 16) Bolinger, D., and Sear, D.A. (1981) *Aspects of Language*, Harcourt Bruce, 3rd edn.
- 17) Bright, J.A. and McGregor, G.P. (1970) *Teaching English as a Second Language*, Longman.
- 18) Bright, J.A. and Piggott, R. (1976) *Handwriting, A Workbook*, Cambridge University Press.